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**THE COMPETITIVENESS ANALYSIS OF DESIGN FIRMS FOR
THE QUALITATIVE GROWTH OF KOREA
BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF PRESENT CONDITIONS OF 25 DESIGN FIRMS
OF 6 COUNTRIES**

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to seek implications for the qualitative growth of design firms of Korea through the analysis of Korean firms and their comparison with the present conditions of 25 design firms of 6 countries. On the basis of the existing models of competitiveness measure, this study extracted 9 key indicators from the viewpoint of the circulation regarding investment, competence, and performance, and systematized sub-indicators of the details. Focusing on these indicators, the questionnaire of the survey was elaborated by differentiating between qualitative elements and quantitative ones. In conclusion, this study recommends design firms in Korea to keep in mind 5 implications: distinctive professionalism, initiative skills, management skills, connectivity and internationality in design business.

Keywords: QUALITATIVE GROWTH, DESIGN FIRM, COMPETITIVENESS

1. INTRODUCTION

This study aims to seek implications for the qualitative growth of design firms of Korea through the analysis of Korean firms and their comparison with the present conditions of 25 design firms of 6 countries. The domestic design industry itself and design firms in Korea have grown up dramatically in terms of quantity; however, unfortunately, it seemed that the quality does not keep up with that. The main reason is as follows. Although, design firms of Korea have developed taking advantages from impressive economic growth of Korea, those firms

have been specialized in only offering their design services to client companies, without constructing various business models. These days, the world of design business is globalized and highly competitive. The design industry in Korea is almost becoming overly saturated and other global leading design firms are overwhelmingly expanding their business areas overseas. The global leading design firms have been diversifying into various design business models, which are not only offering simple design development service but also providing design total consulting and business strategy consulting and creating own brand business. In contrast, the business models of Korean firms are still remaining as simple as they used to be. Therefore, this study attempts to analyze competitiveness of design firms for gaining more economic growth, to explore what the key elements and indicators of competitiveness are, and to seek implications for the qualitative improvement of design firms of Korea by comparing the competitiveness mentioned above with those of 25 design firms.

2. THE CHANGES OF COMPETITIVENESS IN THE DESIGN ENVIRONMENT

As the role of designs has been extended, the concept and the area of designs are redefined with the advent of new business area of designs. Whereas the past design business mostly focused on the area of design creation, the current worldwide leading design firms are emphasizing the research ability. Therefore, the competence of future design business would be up to the contribution in three aspects of business, creating the core value from products,

customer communication and transplanting an innovative business quality. Also, designs would be extended from the exterior production to the integrated modeling along with innovative activities, including the expansion to the area of the social innovation of some companies.

With these environmental changes, there is a huge demand of industrial structural changes and internal efforts from design firms, but the domestic circumstance in Korea is not able to support those demands. In summary, the qualitative growth of design firms is now required along with the quantitative growth of the design business. These changes can be distinguished as internal environmental changes and external environmental changes. The formal one includes the advent of the integrated design consulting, the expansion of design areas, networking between companies and the dissemination of service designs, and the latter one includes the industrial globalization, the innovative competition through designs, increased social requests toward designs, strengthened trends in industry convergence, the improvement of business services, deepening competitions for design industry development among countries, etc. (21st Century Design Forum Final Report(2010)).

3. THE DEFINITION OF COMPETITIVE INDICATORS

3.1. THE CONCEPT OF DESIGN COMPETITIVENESS

While the quantitative growth means design firms' external growth, sales, or total employment, the qualitative growth means the competence level of a company that enables to achieve a sustainable growth. According to academic perspectives, the qualitative growth of company competitiveness can be divided into four categories as industrial structural perspective, resources and competence perspective, BSC perspective and business model perspective. The competitiveness concept of design firms can be defined as the ability for sustainable growth in a good cycle of investment, competence and performance, which can be achieved through a prior investment for building assets with an accumulated competence for better business performances (it will be explained more hereof).

3.2. THE EXTRACTION OF DESIGN COMPETITIVENESS

On the basis of the existing models of competitiveness measure, this study extracted 10 key indicators from the viewpoint of the circulation regarding investment, competence, and performance, and systematized sub-indicators of the details.

The existing models for competitiveness analysis referred in this report are National design competitiveness measure model, Good design firms evaluation model, Korean design firms authorization model, and UK DA authorization model, which have many things in common despite some differences in basic purposes, authentication systems or rating systems. The competitiveness indicators described in this report have been established concerning the major perspective as the analysis model particularly for comparing domestic companies with oversea leading companies. The indicators consisted of 10 sectors: Research/development and education, facility and information system, business structure, profit model, organizational structure and external network, customer relation, design process, design value proposition, financial performance and non-financial performance. To mention briefly the detailed entries, those are the levels of R&D investment, facility/information investment, professional manpower, business initiative, workforce with professionals, external network, the build and practical use of design process, profit structure, and degree of long-term customer retention, sales, award, and intellectual property.

Figure 1. the competitive 10 key indicators of 'investment, competence, and performance.'

The detailed items of research are as followings. First, the verification process is needed to check the preparation in the research and development and the competence establishment in the design concept development. Also, it would be needed to evaluate distinctive training programs or systemized career development programs to build the human power,

along with the investigation about characterized facilities or information systems for differentiated business operations.

Second, in terms of competences, it is necessary to analyze the design philosophy as a design firm, the objective to provide differentiated values to customers, and the core competence to accomplish the value. In terms of industrial structure, it is also necessary to examine the major area of its design business, the structure of the business portfolio including design consulting services and private brands sales, as well as to look into the specialization in specific area or process, the expansion of strategies and brand consulting, major areas of private brands, and the business type such as services and offers based on the design specification depending on customer requests and the development of individual design concepts. In terms of the profit model, performance related profits would be evaluated, for example, post-performance incentives, loyalty incomes, sales revenues and equity dividend incomes. In terms of customer relationships, along with the examination on the classification method of strategic target customer groups, the character of design firms can be different according to the business type of the customer, such as branding companies, ODMs or OEMs. Securing long-term customers is also very critical because the customer loyalty significantly influences the qualitative evaluation of the design business. In terms of organizational structures/networks, it is important in evaluation to have the basic employment size, multi-disciplined staffing, co-work systems among designers, engineers and marketers. In terms of the process, the major distinctive process would be examined to provide differentiated services and offers along with the stipulation of the process to systemize the business.

Finally, in terms of the performance, the accumulating investment and capabilities enable the performance of design firms to produce financial and non-financial outcomes, which can be represented as sales, operating profits, award winnings and results of intellectual property registrations.

4. THE ANALYSIS OF COMPETITIVENESS OF 25 DESIGN FIRMS OF 6 COUNTRIES

The competitiveness of 25 design firms of 6 countries including Korea, USA, UK, Italy, Netherland and Japan has been analyzed using the competitiveness indicators described above, which is 'investment-competence-performance' perspective examined for measuring the competitiveness of design industry and companies.

4.1. THE OUTLINE OF SURVEY

Focusing on these indicators, the questionnaire of the survey was elaborated by differentiating between qualitative elements and quantitative ones based on the competitive key indicators of 'investment, competence, and performance.' The survey, which the representatives of firms answered by e-mail or in person, was done by 10 researchers from 6 countries during two months - September and October, 2010. The standard of selecting target firms is the size - leading, mid-sized, or small sized. According to that rule, 25 design firms were chosen; 10 in Korea and 3 in each different country - the UK, Netherlands, the United States, Italy, and Japan. The one thing noticeable differentiating this selection from existing other research is that this includes as a sample not only renowned design consulting firms with long history but also design brand business firms and small design firms emerging recently. The interview objects have been selected and finalized from the widely nominated 116 companies concerning the easiness of analysis and the practicality. The objects were initially distinguished as leading, medium and start-up companies in order to have valid samples concerning popularity and size in addition to the consideration of products and the balance of the visual area. Specifically, leading companies are world-widely renowned companies, medium companies are medium-sized one showing satisfying performance in general business areas, and start-up companies are 3-5 year old small design studios developing new business areas with showing good performances. With these criteria, 10 domestic companies and 15 companies from 5 countries have been finalized. The list of the research staffs is as following. The 25 design firms listed are as follows. - WolffOlins(UK), SeymourPowell(UK), Think Public(UK), INDES(Netherlands), Flex(Netherlands),

STBY(Netherlands), Lunar(US), One & Co(US), Mike & Maaike(US), Kartell(Italy), Edra(Italy), GiovannoniDesign(Italy), UchidaYoko(Japan), GK Design Group(Japan), Shift(Japan), Mldesign(Korea), D'strict(Korea), Okon(Korea), Ahngraphics(Korea), Mmmg(Korea), Designmall(Korea), Cyphics(Korea), Perception(Korea), Crevate(Korea), Workroom(Korea).

and the United States firstly specialized in providing the product design and developing new brands, and then they expanded their business area to holistic and strategic consulting business. In addition, in the company's growth process, they have grown by collaborating with other sectors, outsourcing, and M & A, and this teaches us that design firms have to make networks of outside more aggressively.

	leading	middle	newly	researcher
UK	WolffOlins SeymourPowell	-	Think Public	Eunkyung Baek
Neder land	INDES	Flex	STBY	Chajoong Kim
USA	Lunar	One & Co	Mike & Maaike	Junggi Sung
Italy	Kartell edra	Giovannoni Design	-	Miyoung Yeo
Japan	UchidaYoko GK Design Group	-	Shift	Seokjin Kim
Korea	Mldesign D'strict Ocon Ahn graphics	mmm Designmall cyphics Perception	Crevate Workroom	Jeho Lee Joomyung Rhi Bosup Kim Soonjong Lee Innseok Park

Table 1. Final Selected 25 Firms

4.2. THE SYNTHESIS OF CHARACTERITICS OF DESIGN FIRMS THROUGH THE KEY INDICATORS

In major indicators, design firms' characteristics are as follows. In the results of the synthesis, the results of each indicator are rearranged by representative cases and implications

4.2.1. The history of firm's growth

The growth process of design firms shows that they firstly were be equipped with the distinctive expertise, and then diversified their business model based on the expertise. Design firms firstly specialized a discriminative expertise after it was established, and then expanded to other business models. Notably firms of the UK, the Netherlands,

Represe ntative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
WolffOli ns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Growth through a strategic/total brand experience consulting from brand design •M&A as affiliated company of Omnicom. Group, 2001 •Strategic/total brand experience consulting service
Seymour Powell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Gradual growth based on product design •M&A as affiliated company of Loewy Group, 2007 - a synergy effect with the brand consulting •Robust, gradual growth
One&Co	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Specialty of product design with the IT field, the mobile device •Securing a high profitability in the HTC's rise to international success from the newcomer •Growth through the M&A
Lunar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Expand to interaction, graphic field from product design •Prudent approach to reinforcement in research function •Outsourcing of research function, specialty strength
INDES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Start up by design consulting service based on design of medical supplier •Diversification of profit models and risks through the production and a sales •Specialty of medical supplier, diversification of profit models
Flex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Start up the design consulting focusing on the practical profit •Expanding own-brand business field •To brand business from design consulting
Ahngraph ics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •To total communication service from editorial + publishing design •Diversification of businesses through a core competence by design

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Diversification of challenging businesses
MI design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Growth by a manufacture business based on design competence from a product design consulting business •Change the manufacture business based on design competence
D'strict	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Space experience and UX design from web service business •Convergence service of a media+art product •Expand through the convergence
Ocon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Start up a animation business, 2002 •Changing the brand business based on contents from brand consulting business •Drastic high value brand business

Table 2. The Case Analysis and Implication about the History of Firm's Growth

4.2.2. Design value proposition and core competence

A study of design firms' value proposition and key competitiveness elements suggests that the fundamental directivity of a firm could be obtained by a discriminative and powerful value proposition. These firms obtained the distinctive expertise by carrying out more aggressive design R&D, user-based research, trend research, and experimental minds based on design-based thoughts. In the success story of all of these 25 design firms, individual markets and distinctive proposition based on client's needs were critical. Finally, the research driven design firms are devoting its efforts to raise the brand awareness through codified user research and developing research methods, and expanding their business model to multifaceted and integrated business based on the expertise.

Representative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
Seymour Powell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Design consulting based on trend forecasting •Oriented a feasible product design •Design consulting business based on trend, consumer studies
INDES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •User centered design: participation on design process •Multidisciplinary team, Independent consumer oriented research

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •User centered design
STBY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Design consulting through the in-depth study on user and design thinking innovation •User studies and design thinking •In-depth study on user
Kartell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Pioneer experimental design •Powerful brand awareness •Create design culture through the support of discovering new designer •Innovation of product culture through the development of new material
GK Design Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Independent 'creative product in Japan' •Original direction 'Japan spirit' •Ekuan Kenji's powerful leadership •Leadership of powerful and creative direction
D'strict	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Futuristic display and interactive 4D technology •Excellent directing – complex content 'Art Mix' •Convergence on technology and content
Ocon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Educational also fun contents - good brand image •Brand business based on character design •Instructive brand Image
mmm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •'Brand like friends' •Consumer intimate brand community policy •Upright design value oriented management •Identification on brand community
Crevate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Service design by innovation •Design process on creation ideas •Service design on creation a innovation
Perception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Design methodology 'Concept modeling' •In-depth communication with clients •'Concept modeling' simulation model

Table 3. The Case Analysis and Implication about Design Value Proposition and Core Competence

4.2.3. Business structure and profit model

A study on design firms' business structure and profit model shows us that they are changing from the supply of professional value of developing products and service to the supply of an integrated full-service. In the past, they were subcontracted to provide design, and now they want to diversify their business model by entering into self-driven brand business. For example, Italian design firms now secure the loyalty business capabilities by obtaining

a high-design initiative. However, other design firms generally have a lower royalty percentage. Another example, as shown in the case of Lunar Design, the distinctive structure is critical for the firms to switch their business model successfully to design consulting business, and entering to foreign markets with some limited features is critical to reduce risk factors. Specific new areas include mainly medical/healthcare sector, and there is a growing trend of providing an integrated design service while they secure the expertise on these sectors. In addition, efforts to strengthen the initiative through their brand business are also important. Foreign firms generally show over 10% of the R&D investment ratio, but domestic firms only show 2-5% of the ratio, and this suggests that the investment to R&D should be stressed.

Representative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
Seymour Powell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Full Service - Design research, Product/service development, engineering •Little importance on loyalty business •Total design service
Think Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Finding a public design field - service design consulting •Social analysis, Social business, social training and workshop •Finding a service design field
INDES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Design consulting / own brand business- ODM •Specialty on Medical/health care/security product •Specialty on Medical/health care/security product
STBY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Design strategy consulting based on design study •Overseas client more than 50% •Hold overseas & international clients
One & Co	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The European + American influence •Experimental + Applied approach •Influence of High tech + low-tech •Initiative by experimental design works
Giovanni Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Full design service from research to design and marketing consulting •Steady-going product - loyalty profit 60-70% •Design service business and development of own brand
MI	•Design consulting 30%, Manufacture 70%

design	•Convergence with design consulting and manufacture business
D'strict	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Commercialize design on space experience •Diversify market shares - profits on AD, rental service, contents •Commercialize design on space experience
Ocon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Kids brand business by 'Pororo' animation - 1200 kinds of goods •Kids' education, theme park, fashion business •Multi source brand Business
Designmall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Loyalty profit 10%, strategy research 30% •Continuous profit structure by annual contract •Continuous, stable profit structure

Table 4. The Case Analysis and Implication about Business Structure and Profit Model

4.2.4. Customer relation

In the customer relationships, securing long-term customers is crucial to the design business. The most firms are much more concerned with maintaining the trust between them and their customers than pioneering a new client. Each firm takes great care to communicate with their client companies. In addition, foreign firms have more open-minded business attitude because they expand and intensify stable network by M&A, comparing with South Korea. Above all, in the relationship between clients and the firms, the more the firms to take the lead of the relationship, and to have many long-term customers, the more stable business is.

Representative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
WolffOlin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Preliminary consulting, deeply design development - client oriented •Reinforce network with Omnicom partner •Reinforce network with holding company 'Omnicom partners'
Lunar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Continuous clients/long time contract •Clients more than 10 years •Long-time clients
One & Co	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Reinforce relationship with existing clients •sales 80% - HTC •Relationship with HTC
Giovanni Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •50% market sales - Italy design firms, 50% - Mass market •Many long-time clients

	•Mass-market design
Uchida Yoko	•Preliminary consulting, than product design •Long-time clients 90% •Long-time clients based on confidence
MI design	•Long-time clients selected •Annual contract •Long-time clients
Ahngraphics	•Continuous relationship by client confidence •Client relationship of risk-taking •client confidence
mmm	•Produce promotional materials - ODM business •Own brand business for young people •Friendly brand •Communication with young generations
Cyphics	•Total design from Styling to service design •Understanding the planning strategy on clients •Accurate understanding on clients
Perception	•Communication capability with clients •Survey satisfaction of clients - once in 2 years •Communication with clients

Table 5. The Case Analysis and Implication about Customer Relation

4.2.5. Design process

In the design process, the codified process is especially developed in prestigious consulting firms of the United Kingdom and the Netherlands. That is to say, the codified process is utilized as a promotional method, so the codification becomes a direct tool to gain profits. In the other hand, Italy is not aware much of the design process, and perceives the process as a critical element in the dimension of strengthening internal capabilities. In short, the codification of the design process is an important business element in the design consulting firms rather than in the design subcontracting firms.

Representative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
WolffOlins	•3 design process -ambition(understanding, insights), creativity, action (delivery) •Refined design process
Seymour Powell	•3 stages design process - Insight, strategy, design •Original design process - SeymourPowell Foresight (SPF)

	•Brand of design methodology
Think Public	•Co-design process •7design process stages - observation, opened survey, movie •7 stages - stipulated design process
INDES	•Stipulated UCID(User Centered Industrial Design) design methodology •User centered research method
edra	•The first priority of designing •Product designer total-directed •pre design, post-development technology •Top priority of emotional design
Kartell	•Design priority •Experimental design by best designer •Own manufacturing facilities •Powerful designer network
D'strict	•Operate 700 young students network - <open innovation network> •Open designer resources
Ocon	•Use personal creative ideas than formal design process •Added value business with production and promotion •Encouragement of feasible ideas of individuals
Ahngraphics	•Co-operation between divisions - planning, editorial, design, marketing •Best art-work •Synergy by co-operation with teams
Crevate	•Stipulated design process -analysis, synthesis, evaluation •Stipulated 7 design process stages

Table 6. The Case Analysis and Implication about Design Process

4.2.6. Organizational structure and external network

In the case of the organizational structure of design firms and external networks, an integrated and interdisciplinary staffing is actively adopted in order to provide an integrated full service. In addition, of overseas firms, there is the corporate culture that stresses the egalitarian and creative organizational structure. In utilizing external networks, they increase the efficiency of business by actively outsourcing whatever is not their core competency, having external personnel and networks, and commit to internationalize their staff. In the case of the United States and the Europe, the firms tend to strengthen international networks by establishing foreign subsidiaries. In conclusion, the design firms

should actively use outsourcing, participate in M&A, and recruit external experts in order to strengthen the business collaboration.

	affiliated company
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Table 7. The Case Analysis and Implication about Organizational Structure and External Network

Representative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
WolffOlin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cultural anthropology, management, economics - Multidisciplinary manpower •Strategy/design/management - 3 coordinative department
Seymour Powell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •All product designer •Coequal organization •Connectivity with Loewy group •Co-operation with overseas researcher
Think Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Multidisciplinary manpower •Coequal organization - project co-operation with humanities and art •Contract professional network
STBY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Re-organization a project •Contract professional network •Industry-university-institute collaboration - conferences, lectures, thesis •All member PhD
Lunar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Outsourcing external professions 'strategy/research' except for product design
Kartell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Collaboration with external designers/design studios •Production outsourcing, direct assembling products for specialization and efficiency
GK Design Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Total design associated company - 8 affiliated companies •Flexible re-organization a project
Ahngraphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Design outsourcing: External writers, designers, photographers •Internal collaboration with planner/editor/designer/marketing manpower
D'strict	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Innovation lab, manufacturing center, media mix - 7 center division •Multidisciplinary manpower for technology innovation, business model innovation •Open innovation by specialist and ordinary people
Ocon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Creator, manager, professional •Flexible project based production •Commercialization internally after co-development in case of brand business •Risk management by independence of

4.2.7. Research/development and education

In the case of design R&D and education, both domestic and international naturally carry out with experience. The core of design R&D includes the previous study on consumers and trend, consumer research, consumers, technology trend, and material development, and these studies aim to brand service design. It is revealed that this research is effective to strengthen firm's brand value and internal capacities. For example, as shown in the case of Seymour Powell, active R&D became the foundation for the growth and jump, and most design firms stressed the necessity for participatory R&D of inside and outside of firms through the industry-academia collaboration network. By contrast, as shown in the case of One & Co., the experimental minds can be a good strategy for small firms to face big firms, and R&D is a critical element to enhance creativity of design.

Representative Firm	Case Analysis & Implication
Seymour Powell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •R&D Institute: future trend, consumer research, precedent design R&D •Future trend, Precedent design R&D
INDES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •R&D department: precedent design R&D •Network with university, joint research by conference, workshop lecture, thesis •Precedent R&D on future trend, consumer research
Giovanni Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Research on technology and market trend
Lunar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Moonshine, volunteer day, elements programs •Creativity and internal design sponsorship program •Community service program •TBA Educational program, Green design development •Variety independent creative program
Think Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Think public award •Workshop with interns and university students •Own brand reinforcement by award, workshop

Kartell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Materials research and innovation with external R&D institution •Continuous R&D on plastic material technology •Development and innovation materials
D'strict	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Innovation lab, public educational program •Publishing design professional books •R&D about 4D technology •Open R&D
Ahngraphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Internal training program •External commissioned education •Digital design institute •Internal/external active education program
mmm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •All activities are R&D •World best product/ world best shop on time meeting •Representatives lecture •Free-form meeting •Self-initiated R&D
Crevate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Produce IDEA card •Organize design educational process •Strengthen brand as a result of R&D

Table 8. The Case Analysis and Implication about Research/ Development and Education

4.3. THE ELICITAION OF MAIN IMPLICATIONS

In the cases of leading domestic and foreign firms, implications are as follows. As noted earlier, five indicators for the qualitative growth of the design firms can be extracted from these cases. In the analysis model of design competitiveness, we extracted qualitative and quantitative indicators such as brand awareness, the degree of sophistication of value proposition, competence to lead market, the initiative in running business, and revenue diversification. In addition, the percentage of long term customers, the degree of strategic cooperation with clients, the ability to secure interdisciplinary staff, and the degree of organizing and utilizing external networks are important elements. Thus, in terms of investment and capacity, we can observe how the proper implementation of detailed indicators and the internalized results are actually linked to financial performance like revenue and operating profit percentage, and to non-financial performance like brand recognition and award records.

We can suggest five capacities such as distinctive professionalism, Initiative skill, management skill,

connectivity, and internationality as what a firm has to care from generalizing implications from each indicator. In other words, it is necessary to have the distinctive expertise in a specific area, and to expand the geographical area of business domestically and internationally, systematizing the design business with the expertise. In addition, there is another area in the direction of the growth where a firm can reach if it expands its business from its unique design area to related activities to an integrated total service, and in this case, it is important to cooperate with inside the organization, customers, and external partners. In the mean time, when design itself is utilized as a core competence in commercializing, it is necessary to think how to raise its brand power. Also, in order to handle non-design problems, it is necessary to think how to raise its management skills.

It is necessary to diversify and upgrade values from design such as the direction of internationalization, specialization, integration, and diversification, and how to systematize organizational and managerial responds is critical. Furthermore, it is considered how to link each sector through networks in order to increase efficiency.

Key Implications	Detail Elements
Distinctive professionalism	Activeness, Value Proposition, Strengthen Brand
Initiative skills	Management Skill, Systematization, Diversification of business fields
Management skills	Originality, Distinction, Specialization, Integration
Connectivity	Long-time partnership, Multidisciplinary, Procedural, International connectivity
Internationality	Connectivity of overseas firm, International member, Overseas Expansion, Overseas market sales

Table 9. The 5 Implications of Qualitative Growth

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion of this study, the implications were drawn from it by comparing the results of investigation and the analysis of success factors derived from 9 indicators mentioned above. In sum,

above all, the essential point of success for design firms is to grow up with distinctive competence. After then, exploring the diversified business models, they can be firmly established with a stable corporate structure. In addition, it was found that design firms in the United Kingdom, Netherlands, and the United States are actively in collaboration with other area; outsourcing and M&A activities are popular. On the other hand, the operation manner of the target firms in Italy primarily is characterized in an apprenticeship business and the union of small clusters. Investing in research and development (R&D) actively is critical to its growth; it is mainly dealing with user-based research, trend research, and experimental design development based on design thinking. When it comes to business structure and profit model, offering the integrated full-service to clients was a general trend; however, in Italy, the proportion of brand business is comparably and especially high, the firms are getting their loyalty profits from that sector. Also, the UK and Netherlands tend to develop stipulated design process and utilize it as promotion methodology of

design strategy consulting. Concerning organizational structure and external network, it is crucial to pursue multidisciplinary manpower, to prepare the horizontal and egalitarian organizational structure, and to provide various activities in order to encourage spontaneous creativities of design competence. In conclusion, it is needed to construct infrastructure by the government to foster the desirable business system of design industry for design firms, client companies, and educational institutes. Moreover, this study recommends design firms in Korea to keep in mind 5 implications: distinctive professionalism, initiative skills, management skills, connectivity and internationality in design business.

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